

The Theory of Electrophoresis of Liquid Drops*

D. N. Biswas and M. Sengupta

The application of the Booth theory of electrophoresis of liquid drops to actual experimental results, as developed in a previous communication, has been extended to Mooney's data for the electrophoresis of Stanolind drops in distilled water and in some electrolyte solutions. Calculation of electrophoretic mobility for different drop sizes in an electrolyte solution of constant concentration, has been carried out for two possible types of charge distribution in the inner fluid, namely the interfacial layer type and the diffuse double layer type. It has been shown that the theoretical equation for the diffuse double layer type of charge distribution reproduces more or less correctly the general nature of the electrophoretic mobility vs. size curve for a suitable choice of the values of ζ potential and the ratio of the double layer thicknesses in the two fluids.

The theory of electrophoresis of liquid drops differs from that of solid spherical particles in two important respects. The condition of motion at the interface involved in the two cases are different with the result that the boundary conditions to be applied to hydrodynamic equations at the interface are quite different in the two cases. Also, the possible dissolution of electrolytes in the fluid of the drop would give rise to a charge and potential distribution inside the drop analogous to that in the outer solution which would give rise to hydrodynamic body forces within the fluid drop. Both the above factors would give rise to complications and would modify the electrophoresis equation of solid particles in the case of liquid drops.

The electrophoresis equation for liquid drops has been worked out by Booth¹ for some particular types of charge and potential distribution inside the liquid drop. In a previous communication² the application of Booth equation to actual experimental results has been made for the case of electrophoresis measurement data of Mooney³ for some organic oil droplets in distilled water. In the present communication the calculations have been extended to Mooney's electrophoresis data for Stanolind emulsions in distilled water and in some electrolyte solutions.

Booth electrophoresis equation for liquid drops. The assumptions underlying the derivation of the Booth equation are: that the macroscopic values of the dielectric constant, viscosity, and electrical conductivity of the two fluids hold also in the double layer region; that both fluids are incompressible and the drop remains spherical even when in motion; that the velocities involved are small so that simplified hydrodynamic equations can be applied; and finally that the externally applied field is in both the liquids linearly superimposed on the internal field due to ionic charges so that the ionic potential in both the fluids remains spherically symmetrical. Under these assumptions the expression for the

* Presented at the 4th Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society held at Vallabh Vidyanagar, Gujrat State, 1966.

1. Booth, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 1331.

2. Sengupta, to be published.

3. Mooney, *Phys. Rev.*, 1924, 23, 396.

electrophoretic velocity for liquid droplets of radius a under an applied field E has been given by Booth as

$$U = \frac{E}{6\pi\eta_1(3\eta_2+2\eta_1)} \left[\epsilon_1 \zeta \left\{ 3\eta_2(1+\lambda F_1) + 2\eta_1(1-\lambda F_2) \right\} - \frac{5\epsilon_2\eta_1(1+\lambda)}{a^3} \int_0^a z^3 \frac{d\psi_2(z)}{dz} dz \right] \quad (1)$$

where $F_1(b)$ is the Henry function

$$F_1(b) = \frac{1}{3}b^3 - \frac{1}{6}b^4 - \frac{1}{12}b^4 + \frac{1}{12}b^5 + \frac{1}{2}b^4 e^b \text{Ei}(b) \left(1 - \frac{1}{12}b^2\right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and $F_2(b)$ is the Booth function

$$F_2(b) = \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{2}b - \frac{1}{2}b^2 + \frac{1}{2}b^3 - \frac{1}{2}b^4 e^b \text{Ei}(b) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Here } \text{Ei}(b) = \int_b^\infty \frac{e^{-x}}{x} dx \quad ; \quad \lambda = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}{2\sigma_1 + \sigma_2} \quad ; \quad b = ka, \quad k^2 \text{ is the Debye}$$

Hückel parameter $k^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2}{\epsilon_1 k T} \sum n_i z_i^2$; and $\eta_1, \epsilon_1, \sigma_1$ and $\eta_2, \epsilon_2, \sigma_2$ are the viscosity coefficients, dielectric constants and specific conductivities of the outer solution and the inner fluid respectively. ζ is the electrical potential at the interface. The plots of $F_1(b)$ and $F_2(b)$ as functions of b have been given by Booth¹.

The potential distribution in the outer solution has been assumed in the above deduction to be of the spherically symmetrical Debye Hückel type. The potential distribution ψ_2 in the inner fluid depends, however, on the nature of the charge distribution in it. Booth has considered three possible types of charge distribution in the inner fluid, of which we shall mention only two. These are:

(A) the charge in the inner fluid is all located in a thin layer adjacent to the interface; the potential due to it is therefore everywhere constant inside the drop and is given by $\psi_2 = \zeta$. In this case equation (1) reduces to

$$U = \frac{E\epsilon_1\zeta}{6\pi\eta_1(3\eta_2+2\eta_1)} \left[3\eta_2(1+\lambda F_1) + 2\eta_1(1-\lambda F_2) \right] \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

This case is of particular interest to us because electrolytes would be virtually insoluble in non-polar hydrocarbon droplets and consequently the charge in such droplets would be located in the interfacial layer.

(B) The charge in the inner fluid is distributed as in a diffuse double layer. The general equation (1) reduces in this case to

$$U = \frac{E\epsilon_1\zeta}{6\pi\eta_1(3\eta_2+2\eta_1)} \left[3\eta_2(1+\lambda F_1) + 2\eta_1(1-\lambda F_2) + 5\eta_1(1+\lambda)F_3F_4 \frac{(1+b)}{b^2} \right] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where $F_3(b')$ and $F_4(b')$ are Booth functions of b' ($=k'a$), $1/k'$ being the thickness of the diffuse double layer in the inner fluid:

$$F_3(b') = [e^{b'}(b'-1) + e^{-b'}(b'+1)]^{-1} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$F_4(b') = e^{b'}(b'^2 - 3b' + 3) - e^{-b'}(b'^2 + 3b' + 3) \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Application of Booth equation to actual experimental results.—Experimental results of mobility measurements for particles of varying sizes in a solution of constant electrolyte concentration are most suitable for verification of the theoretical equations. Since there is no reason why ζ should then change, a constant characteristic value for this quantity may be assumed for each system, which can further be used as an adjustable parameter for fitting the theoretical equation to the experimental results. The experimental determination of the mobility of particles of varying sizes in solutions of constant electrolyte concentration has not been carried out extensively. However, from among the meagre results recorded in literature the data of Mooney³ appear to be the most suitable for verification of the theoretical equations, because of the absence of any type of contaminants in the systems which would otherwise disastrously affect the fluid motion within the drop.

Mooney's results were obtained in a closed vertical tubular cataphoresis cell of length 20 cm. and diameter 6 mm. The applied voltage was 199, wherefrom after subtracting 1.5 volts for the counter E.M.F., the effective voltage was found to be 197.5, and the potential gradient 9.875 V/cm. Particle diameters and velocities were recorded in terms of divisions in the eye-piece micrometer scale, each division being equal to 0.001092 cm. The distilled water used was estimated, from specific conductivity measurements of the emulsions to have an impurity content of 2×10^{-3} N. Precautions were taken to ensure uniformity and constancy of temperature; curiously however the temperature is not recorded. In all cases the motion was in the direction of the field, indicating a negative charge on the drops. The oil emulsions were prepared without the use of any stabilisers or ingredients added to make the density of oil equal to that of water. From the results of mobility measurements recorded for different oils, only those for emulsions of "Stanolind", a liquid paraffin (heavy) manufactured by the Standard Oil Company of Indiana, Illinois, in distilled water and in some electrolyte solutions, will be used for the present calculations.

The mobility values for different drop radii were obtained from the mobility vs. drop size figure given by the author by first suitably photomagnifying it and then copying onto graph paper. A temperature of 25°C was assumed, and the values of viscosity coefficient and dielectric constant of water were taken to be 8.95 m. poise and 78.54 respectively. The viscosity value of Stanolind (present trade name USP-31) in centistokes at 25°C was evaluated from the viscosity (Seybolt universal second units) vs. temperature (°F) graph obtained through courtesy of M/s. Standard Oil Company, Indiana, U.S.A. As the factor for conversion from SUS units to centistokes was available only for 100°F, therefore the slight variation in its magnitude over the small temperature difference involved was taken into account and the viscosity value in centistokes at 25°C (77°F) was obtained by plotting the log viscosity (centistokes) values at 105°F, 100°F and 95°F (all obtained by using the conversion factor for 100°F) against the reciprocal of the corresponding absolute temperature and extrapolating to 77°F. This procedure is

considered to be sufficiently accurate for the present purpose. ($\eta_{\text{Stanolind}} (25^\circ\text{C}) = 1.194$ poise).

Calculations have been carried out for both the possible types of charge distribution in the inner fluid mentioned above, namely (1) the interfacial layer type and (2) the diffuse double layer type. The value of the Booth function $F_2(ka)$ as also the Henry function $F_1(ka)$ for various values of ka , necessary for these calculations were obtained from the results given by Booth¹. The figure given for $F_2(ka)$ and $F_1(ka)$ curves was suitably photo-magnified and then copied onto graph paper. The values of the Booth functions $F_3(b')$, $F_4(b')$ and particularly of the quantity F_3F_4/b'^2 necessary for calculations in the case of the second type of charge distribution considered were obtained from the plot of the function F_3F_4/b'^2 as given in the previous communication cited². This of course makes it necessary (similarly as in the ref. cited) to restrict the calculation from $b'=0.25$ to $b'=10$. Also for calculations in this case, the thickness of the inner double layer, $1/k'$, the actual magnitude of which is determined by the extent of electrolyte solubility in the liquid hydrocarbon of the drop, arises as a new unknown quantity. In want of more specific information, it has however been considered more advantageous for the present calculations to take the ratio of the double layer thicknesses in the two fluids b/b' as an adjustable parameter. Finally the ζ -potential, the value of which under the experimental conditions is a characteristic constant for each particular system, can be considered to be a second adjustable parameter for fitting the theoretical curves with the experimental points.

The results for Stanolind drops in distilled water, 10^{-4}N NaOH solution, 10^{-4}N HCl solution and 10^{-3}N NaOH solution are recorded respectively in Tables I to IV and shown graphically in Figs. 1 to 4. The required values of ζ -potential for both types of calculations (ζ_1 and ζ_2) as also of the double layer thickness ratio b/b' (two different suitable values, generally) required for the second type of calculation are recorded at the appropriate places.

Fig. 1. Electrophoretic mobility of Stanolind droplets in distilled water (Mooney's data). 1— theoretical curve according to the equation 4 ($\zeta_1 = 74.4$ mV). 2a, 2b— theoretical curves according to the equation 5; $b/b' = 25$, $\zeta_2 = 8.01$ mV., and $b/b' = 10$, $\zeta_2 = 11.83$ mV. respectively.

Fig. 2. Electrophoretic mobility of Stanolind droplets in 10^{-4}N NaOH solution (Mooney's data). 1— theoretical curve according to equation 4 ($\zeta_1 = 84.06$ mV/). 2a, 2a' and 2b— theoretical curves according to equation 5; $b/b' = 15$, $\zeta_2 = 11.78$ mV, $\zeta_2 = 9.28$ mV, and $b/b' = 10$, $\zeta_2 = 13.2$ mV respectively.

Diameter (scale (divs.))	b	b'	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃ F ₄ /b' ²	U ₁ (scale divs. per sec.)	U ₂ (scale divs. per sec.)
Table I. Distilled water. b/b'=10, ζ ₁ 11.83 mV. b/b'=25, ζ ₂ 8.01 mV. ζ ₁ 74.4 mV. k=1.4697 × 10 ⁵ cm ⁻¹ .							
0.25	20.064	2.006	0.667	1.758	9.0	4.618	2.692
		0.802			9.90		1.955
0.50	40.126	4.013	0.788	1.848	7.25	4.828	3.846
		1.604			9.90		3.193
0.75	60.188	6.019	0.848	1.894	5.80	4.932	4.449
		2.408			8.65		4.231
1.00	80.253	8.025	0.888	1.918	4.80	5.00	4.822
		3.210			8.00		5.082
1.50	120.38	12.038	0.924	1.939	3.50	5.063	5.191
		4.81			6.60		6.144

Table II. 10⁻⁴ N NaOH solution. b/b'=15, ζ₁ 11.78 mV. ζ₂ 9.28 mV. b/b'=10, ζ₁ 13.2 mV, ζ₂ 84.06 mV. k=3.2865 × 10⁵ cm⁻¹.

0.25	44.863	2.991	0.818	1.864	8.15	5.517	4.613(3.635)
		4.486			6.880		4.500
0.50	89.727	5.982	0.888	1.924	5.85	5.650	6.249(4.922)
		8.973			4.44		5.526
0.75	134.59	8.972	0.921	1.939	4.40	5.715	6.933(5.462)
		13.459			3.14		5.800
1.00	179.45	11.963	0.948	1.955	3.52	5.769	7.338(5.780)
		17.945			2.195		5.468

Table III. 10⁻⁴ N HCl solution. b/b'=15, ζ₁ 5.75 mV.; b/b'=10, ζ₁ 7.72 mV. ζ₁ 53.8 mV.
k=3.2865 × 10⁵ cm⁻¹.

0.25	44.863	2.991	0.818	1.864	8.15	3.531	2.259
		4.486			6.88		2.631
0.30	89.727	5.982	0.888	1.924	5.85	3.616	3.050
		8.973			4.44		3.231
0.75	134.59	8.972	0.921	1.939	4.40	3.658	3.385
		13.459			3.14		3.391
1.00	179.45	11.963	0.948	1.955	3.52	3.692	3.582

Table IV. 10⁻³N NaOH solution. b/b'=50, ζ₁ 5.50 mV. ζ₁ 128.0 mV. k=1.0372 × 10⁵ cm⁻¹.

0.25	141.60	2.832	0.939	1.939	8.30	8.757	6.055
0.50	283.21	5.664	0.970	1.970	6.04	8.846	8.615
0.75	424.80	8.496	0.982	1.970	4.63	8.882	9.841
1.00	566.40	11.328	0.985	1.970	3.70		10.453

The slight difference in the values of the functions F₁, F₂, and F₃F₄/b'² from those in the ref. 2, for corresponding values of b and b', is due to their estimation from graphical plots. The lower recorded figures in Tables I, II, III correspond in each case to the second given set of b/b' and ζ₁ values. The bracketed U₂ values in Table II correspond to the ζ₂ 9.28 mV. value in the first given set of b/b' and ζ₁ values.

From a comparison of the nature of the theoretical curves with the experimental points as shown in the figures, certain general conclusions can be drawn. Considering that the ζ -potential appears in both the equations (4) and (5) only as a multiplicative constant it is seen that equation (4) does not reproduce correctly the nature of the observed variation of mobility with drop size. Equation (5) is more successful; however, too large a value of b/b' , is seen to give a steeper variation of mobility with size than is actually observed. By judicious choice of the parameters b/b' and ζ , equation (5) can be expected to reproduce the observed variation of mobility over the entire range of drop sizes. However, in order for this to be decided conclusively by extending the calculation over the entire corresponding range of b values, it is necessary (for the above chosen values of the ratio b/b' , for example) to first extend the plot of the function $F_2 F_4 / b'^2$ over a considerably larger range of b' values than is available at present (ref. 2). This work is in progress.

It is to be noted that the ζ -potential values required by the more successful equation (5) are very small in magnitude and might be considered unacceptable. It should be remembered however that one of the important assumptions underlying the deduction of the Booth equation (1) is that $e\psi \ll kT$. This would entail therefore that only in case the ζ potential values actually required are found to be small in magnitude, would the calculations be self-consistent.

Fig. 3. Electrophoretic mobility of Stanolind droplets in 10^{-4} N HCl solution (Mooney's data). 1—theoretical curve according to equation 4 ($\zeta_1=53.8$ mV). 2a, 2b—theoretical curves according to equation 5; $b/b'=15$, $\zeta_2=5.75$ mV and $b/b'=10$, $\zeta_2=7.72$ mV respectively.

Fig. 4. Electrophoretic mobility of Stanolind droplets in 10^{-2} N NaOH solution (Mooney's data). 1—theoretical curve according to equation 4 ($\zeta_1=128.0$ mV). 2—theoretical curve according to equation 5; $b/b'=5$, $\zeta_2=5.50$ mV.

Finally, it may be mentioned that certain discrepancies, such as the observed finite electrophoretic mobility of gas bubbles, throw some doubts regarding the correctness of the Booth equations. A possibly serious error in the formulation of the boundary conditions to the hydrodynamic equations at the interface, involved in the deduction of equation (1), has already been pointed out elsewhere^{3,5}. However, compared to the other liquid drop electrophoresis equation available in literature⁴, the Booth equation is undoubtedly far

4. Taylor and Wood, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1957, 53, 523.

5. Sengupta, to be published.

superior both in regard to mathematical rigour and general treatment (see ref. 2). It may therefore be concluded that a more exhaustive verification of this equation through more precise fresh measurement of electrophoretic mobility of oil droplets of different viscosities, particularly in the smaller range of sizes, and preferably in solutions of very low electrolyte concentrations, is necessary before any final conclusion can be made. Also, if the electrolyte solubility in the oil phase be determined separately and care taken to ensure solubility equilibrium before the electrophoresis measurements, then b' can be determined exactly beforehand and need no longer be taken as an adjustable parameter. This would make the verification of the theoretical equation more crucial.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA-9.

Received, November 25, 1966.